

ISic1202

Epitaph of Kalliboula

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tuff

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8701

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 25 cm

Width 38 cm

Depth 22 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30-50 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: n/a mm

Text

1. [K]αλλιβούλας

Apparatus

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Kalliboula

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492806

EDR 150014

EDCS 39101566

PHI 140686

PHI 175725

Bibliography

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Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 61 no.9 fig.24

Bechtel, F., Collitz, H., Meister, R. C., Bezenberger, A. 1884-1915. Sammlung der griechischen Dialekt-Inschriften. Göttingen. At 5209a

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